

Phenotype Discrimination Based on Pressure Signals by Transfer Learning Approaches

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Abstract. Computational Ethology is the study of the animal behavior using advances in the field of Computer Vision and Artificial Intelligence. This field of research allows scientists to analyse and characterise behaviors and find out the differences that exist between distinct diseases or disorders for pharmacological studies. In this work we will analyse the data recorded with a multisensor system composed of a top video camera and a piezoelectric pressure sensor that records the movements of an animal. Specifically, this work aims to answer the research question of whether it is possible to differentiate phenotype of an animal model using transfer learning over the pressure signal alone. To do this, the piezoelectric signal will be analysed in the frequency domain by computing its spectrogram, and we segment the chunks corresponding to the locomotion events, previously detected. Convolutional neural models previously trained will be used for classification by applying a transfer learning approach. The results show that an accuracy of more than 96% is obtained and the confirmation that it is possible to classify phenotypes with the data obtained with pressure sensors.

Keywords: Animal Ethology, Piezoelectric, Pressure sensor, Locomotion, Animal behavior, Tracking, Signal processing, Binary classification

1 Introduction

Ethology is defined as the discipline that studies the animal behavior in terms of its phenomenological, causal, ontogenetic and evolutionary aspects, in order to provide answers to the causes and development that animal behavior undergoes, as well as to understand how it is performed [1], bearing in mind that behavior is understood as the set of muscular responses of a living being as a consequence of an external stimulus and internal motivation [2]. In this sense, Computational Ethology (CE) incorporates the advances in Computer Vision and Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the study of animal behavior, allowing to automate and increase the precision in experimentation analysis, and also giving more information to characterize the behaviors. By analysing the behavior is possible to extract characteristics from them that allow us to describe them quantitatively. From a pharmacological point of view, ethological experimentation give another possibility to test new medicines, as it is capable of quantifying behaviors and comparing them between different subjects. In addition, it is possible to generate animal models with genetic modifications that provide study

subjects with anatomy, physiology or response to a pathogen that are sufficiently similar to humans to be able to extrapolate the results obtained to them [3]. The most commonly used models in research are rodents, especially mice and rats, zebra fish, amphibians and reptiles, birds and other small animals.

There exist several kinds of sensors to carry out experiments in CE such as depth and RGB video cameras, accelerometers, magnetometers, gyroscopes and pressure sensors, among others. In the study of behavior, it is interesting to use sensors that are as non-invasive as possible. In this sense, pressure sensors can be useful as they allow data to be collected without interfering with the behavior of the animals, such as the Phenotypix platform [4], which offers a high sensitivity for detecting pressure changes, making it possible to detect freezing, breathing and heartbeats in mice.

Apart from sensors, there are numerous techniques developed in the field of Computer Vision and AI that are used to process the experimental data in CE.

DeepLabCut is a markerless motion tracking system based on transfer learning and it is easily tailored to the specific experimental setting. Recently, it has been used to analyse stroke recovery in rodent [5], X-ray video of rodent locomotion [6], cardiac physiology assessment in zebra fish [7], multi animal pose estimation and tracking [8]. Bonsai [9] is another tracking framework that can perform other tasks, such as data acquisition and experiment control. LEAP [10] and SLEAP [11] are both tools based on Deep Neural Network for pose estimation and, being SLEAP specifically designed for social interaction.

JAABA is a well-known application that uses a semi-supervised machine learning algorithm for automatic annotation of animal behavior [12]. There are also neural networks that identify the genetics of a mouse by analyzing grooming behavior [13] and algorithms based on deep learning such as DeepEthogram, which classifies behaviors in a supervised manner from raw pixels [14]. Convolutional neural networks are also very useful for classification and behavior detection using frames and currently also 3D convolutional networks for behavior automatic classification [15] and for grooming detection of mouse [16]. On this matter, transfer learning is a tool that takes advantage of pre-trained networks to develop models instead of training from scratch, decreasing the amount of data and computation time [17,18].

Thus, this paper proposes a research question based on the hypothesis that an strain classifier can be implemented from the pressure signals after segmentation based on the images recorded by a top video camera by using pre-trained models and transfer learning. These results are important in Pharmacology to improve the understanding of the behavior in animals, establishing differences between two phenotypes quantitatively. There are some works in the literature that provide solutions to this behavioral phenotyping problem. One of these classifiers is carried out by using video recordings, where a SVM is fed with a 32-dimensional feature vector that indicates the relative frequency of each of the 8 behaviors of interest [19]. Another example analyses the percentage of time in open arms, total distance traveled and percentage of time in the center with k-Nearest Neighbor from RGB-D images [20].

In the next section, the materials and the recording system is explained, together with the data processing, the classification methods and their evaluation. Next, the results of the validation test are described, showing the accuracy, precision, recall and F1 score for the classification models. Last section makes a discussion about the results of the research question.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Animals

The experiments were carried out with 12 mice with two different strains and the dataset are divided as follow:

- 7 wild-type (WT)¹ mice with a total duration of recordings of 4 hours and 20 minutes
- 5 transgenic Fmr1-knockout (Fmr1-KO)² mice with a total duration of recordings of 4 hours and 20 minutes

The recordings took place during the light period and it was the first time these models were in contact with the recording system. All animals were bred in the laboratory animal facility in collective cages, and transferred to individual cages for the duration of the experiments. Animals were kept on a 12 h/12 h light/dark cycle, provided with nesting material and food and water *ad libitum*. All experiments were performed during the light period under constant mild luminosity (60-70 Lux). All experimental procedures were performed in accordance with EU directives relating to the protection of animals used for experimental and scientific purposes, in accordance with the reference work [4].

2.2 Behavioral Data Acquisition

The pressure sensor environment used to record the experiments is composed of an opaque-walled cage and a base resting on several piezoelectric sensors at a sampling rate of 20 kHz [4]. This platform is mounted on a table stabilized with pressured air in order to remove environmental motion noise. A Logitech HD Webcam C270 video camera is placed on top of the cage to record the experiment at 25 fps as shown in figure 1.

Animals were introduced individually into the platform and the walls and cage were cleaned with 70% ethanol before each recording. To visualise the piezoelectric signal obtained during the recordings, Spike2 software (CED, Cambridge, UK) was connected to a computer where the data were stored for later analysis. At the same time the videos were recorded with the top camera and stored separately from the signals. The data were then processed with Bonsai [9], MATLAB (Mathworks, Natick, MA, USA) and Python [21]. The length of the videos range from 20 minutes to 1 hour.

¹ Wild-type gene is a term used to describe a gene when it is found in its natural, non-mutated (unchanged) form.

² Fmr1-knockout (Fmr1-KO) mice may be useful for studying behavioral and synaptic abnormalities associated with Fragile X Syndrome.

Fig. 1. The experimental platform.

2.3 Data Processing

Fig. 2. Data processing pipeline.

Once the data are collected after the acquisition phase, they are processed to obtain the images for the classification algorithms. The pipeline of this process is shown in figure 2 and described below:

1. Check whether the video has the correct format and duration. If not the multimedia framework ffmpeg [22] is used to change the video format and correct its duration by changing the frame rate. This framework can benefit from GPU acceleration and its functions can be automated with Python or MATLAB scripts.
2. Compute the x and y position of the animal centroid through videos using Bonsai software carrying out the steps shown in figure 3:

- (a) Apply an affine transformation to align the video with the window frame.
 - (b) Crop the video to center the region of interest to the platform where the animal will move.
 - (c) Apply an binarization to change colors to gray scale. This step facilitates the animal segmentation. The function checks if the color is darker than a predefined threshold to paint the pixel white and otherwise black. The result is an image in black and white where the animal is white and the background is in black. In case there are objects apart from the animal, these object will be seen in white too.
 - (d) Find contours based on the color changes.
 - (e) Take binary region and select the largest one to avoid objects out of interest.
 - (f) Compute the centroid of the largest binary region in pixels.
 - (g) Convert centroid from pixels to cm by using a proportional relationship taking into account the size of the recording platform.
3. Smooth the x and y centroid computing the average of 3 consecutive points. This eliminates possible positional errors and filter the trajectory of the animal.
 4. Synchronize the time scale from of the centroid and the piezoelectric signal, taking into account the time offset between both time scales and skipping the first seconds of the video before the animal appears on the recording platform.
 5. Apply a locomotion filter to detect periods when the animal is walking using a MATLAB script with a minimum velocity of 2.5 cm/s and a minimum distance of 2.5 cm for each period.
 6. Obtain the spectrogram using Chronux library and Sonic Visualizer for the whole signal and segment the time periods corresponding to valid locomotion events.
 7. Obtain the images from these spectrograms and save them to train and test the classification models.

Table 1. Parameters for spectrogram computation with Chronux library.

Parameters	Value 1	Value 2	Default values
Window size (s)	1	2	-
Windows step (s)	0.1	0.2	-
Tapers	[4, 2]	[3, 5]	[3, 5]: A numeric vector [TW K] where TW is the time-bandwidth product and K is the number of tapers, less than or equal to 2TW-1
Frequency of interest (Hz)	[1.5 - 40]	[4 - 112]	[0 - Fs/2] (Fs: sampling frequency)

Related to the Chronux library³, there are some parameters which can be tuned, such as window size, window step, number of tapers or frequency of interest. The window size is how long the number of samples is in every computation

³ <http://chronux.org/>

Fig. 3. Bonsai pipeline for video processing.

Table 2. Parameter for spectrogram computation with Sonic Visualizer.

Parameter	Value	Range of values
Colour	Green	[Green, Sunset, ... , Wasp, Ice, ...]
Scale	dB	[Linear, Meter, dB ² , dB, Phase]
Window size	256	[32, 64, 128, 256, 512, ... , 16384, 32768]
Overlap	93.75%	[none, 25%, 50%, 75%, 87.5%, 93.75%]
Show	All bins	[All Bins, Peak Bins, Frequencies]
Scale	Linear	[Linear, Log]

and the window step is the size of the displacement to take the next sample. Modifying the number of tapers is a way to control the degree of the smoothing in the spectrogram and the frequency of interest allows to limit the frequency range. Table 1 shows the parameters used in the processing with Chronux library and the figure 4 shows two spectrogram chunks obtained from the locomotion periods for a wild type (a) and transgenic Fmr1-KO (b) models with Chronux library. This spectrogram has been calculated for a frequency band of interest of 4-112 Hz, a window size of 1 s, a window step 0.1 s and number of tapers [3, 5].

Fig. 4. Samples of spectrogram images computed with Chronux for a segmented signal chunk during locomotion time for a) wild type and b) transgenic Fmr1-KO model.

For the spectrogram computed with Sonic Visualizer, the parameter tuning was carried out manually searching for the configuration that highlights the differences in the spectrogram for different strains. This configuration is shown in the table 2 and the figure 5 shows two spectrogram chunks obtained from the locomotion periods for a wild type (a) and transgenic Fmr1-KO (b) models with Sonic Visualizer software.

2.4 Pre-trained Models

To classify the images between wild type and Fmr1-KO models we have used pre-trained models by applying transfer learning. This process takes advantage of models that have been previously trained with a large amount of data and high hardware resources, so that to adapt it to a new dataset, only the last layer has to be trained instead of starting from scratch. In this work we have used the following convolutional neural networks:

- AlexNet [23] is a well-known convolutional neural network which won the ImageNet Large-Scale Visual Recognition Challenge (ILSVRC) in 2012. ImageNet is a dataset of over 15 million labeled high-resolution images belonging to 22,000 categories. However, a subset of ImageNet with 1000 images for 1000 categories was used for the ILSVRC. The architecture of AlexNet is

Fig. 5. Samples of spectrogram images computed with Sonic Visualizer for a segmented signal chunk during locomotion time for a) wild type and b) transgenic Fmr1-KO model.

composed of five convolutional layers and three fully connected layers with a final 1000-way softmax.

- GoogLeNet [24] is a deep convolutional neural network with 22 layers winner of ILSVRC in image classification and detection in 2014. This network is based on the Inception architecture that consists of making the network wider than deeper in order to take into account different scales.
- ResNet50 [25] is a deep convolutional neural network which uses learning residual functions to train the model. It won the ILSVRC15 in image detection and localization with the ImageNet dataset doing the task of classifying the image into one of the 1000 categories in the ImageNet hierarchy.

2.5 Model Training and Evaluation

The question presented in this contribution is formulated as a binary classification problem that aims to discriminate between wild type (0 class) and Fmr1-KO (1 class) models. The spectrogram images previously generated during the locomotion periods will be used for training the classifiers, described in the subsection 2.4, along with the training parameters shown in the table 3.

Table 3. Training parameters

Parameter	Value
Solver	Adam
Learning rate	0.0001
Mini batch size	52
L2 Regularization	0.0001
Folds for Cross-validation	5

The image dataset is divided into two parts, one for training and one for testing with a proportion of 80% and 20%, respectively. To train the models, a 5-fold cross-validation has been applied over the training dataset, dividing it into 5 folds. For each of the 5 training sessions, a model is trained with 4 folds and the 5th is used as development set, repeating this process alternating the development set and obtaining 5 different models. For validation, the best of the 5 previous models is chosen according to the accuracy and it is applied to the test set.

The image size is variable depending on the model, so the dimensions must be 227 x 227 x 3 for AlexNet and 224 x 224 x 3 for ResNet50 and GoogLeNet.

The models were implemented in MATLAB using an Intel(R) Core(TM) i9-9880H computer with 64 GB of RAM and a NVIDIA Quadro RTX 3000 GPU. The execution times for training and validation, the number of layers and the learnables parameters are showed in the table 4.

Table 4. Execution time for training and evaluation (cross validation), number of layers and number of learnables parameters.

Algorithm	Execution time	Layers	Total learnables
AlexNet	≈ 35min	25 (depth 8)	56 876 418
ResNet50	≈ 4h	177 (depth 50)	23 538 690
GoogLeNet	≈ 2h	144 (depth 22)	5 975 602

3 Results

After obtaining the images showed in the section 2.3, we have trained the models explained in the section 2.4. In this chapter we show the results of accuracy, precision, recall and F1 score for the validation tests. The following parameters have been used for the experiments:

- Minimum locomotion duration of 2500 ms
- Sampling window size of 2500 ms
- Window step of 100 ms

3.1 Results for Spectrogram Computed with Chronux library

Table 5 shows the accuracy, precision, recall and F1 score results after using the AlexNet, GoogLeNet and ResNet50 networks for the images calculated using Chronux library with 1 second window size and 0.1 seconds window step for frequencies from 4 Hz to 112 Hz. An accuracy of value of 99.47% has been reached with GoogLeNet and ResNet50 for a number of tapers of [3, 5] and 100% with AlexNet for a number of tapers of [4, 2]. The precision, recall and F1 score values are very similar and above 0.97 for the three models.

Table 5. Results for spectrogram images computed with Chronux library for 1 second window size and 0.1 seconds window step.

Tapers	3 - 5				4 - 2			
	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
AlexNet	98.40%	1.00	0.97	0.98	100.00%	1.00	1.00	1.00
GoogLeNet	99.47%	0.99	1.00	0.99	99.47%	1.00	0.99	0.99
ResNet50	99.47%	0.99	1.00	0.99	99.47%	0.99	1.00	0.99

Table 6. Results for spectrogram images computed with Chronux library for 2 seconds window size and 0.5 seconds window step.

Tapers	3 - 5				4 - 2			
	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
AlexNet	98.93%	0.98	1.00	0.99	96.79%	0.93	1.00	0.97
GoogLeNet	97.86%	0.97	0.99	0.98	97.33%	0.97	0.98	0.97
ResNet50	99.47%	0.99	1.00	0.99	97.86%	0.97	0.99	0.98

Similarly, table 6 shows the accuracy, precision, recall and F1 score results for 2 seconds window size and 0.5 seconds window step. Accuracy of values of 99.47% and 97.86% have been reached with ResNet50 for a number of tapers of [3, 5] and [4, 2], respectively. The precision, recall and F1 score values are very similar and above 0.93 for the three models.

3.2 Results for Spectrogram Computed with Sonic Visualizer

Table 7 shows the accuracy, precision, recall and F1 score results for validation test after training the AlexNet, GoogLeNet and ResNet50 networks with the images from Sonic Visualizer spectrograms. An accuracy value of 100% has been reached with AlexNet and more than 96% with GoogLeNet and ResNet50. In relation to precision, recall and F1 score, all three models return similar values above 0.93.

Table 7. Results for spectrogram images computed with Sonic Visualizer.

Window size - overlap	256 - 93.75%			
	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
AlexNet	100.00%	1.00	1.00	1.00
GoogLeNet	96.26%	0.93	0.99	0.96
ResNet50	96.79%	0.95	0.98	0.97

4 Conclusions and Future Work

This paper proposes a research question based on the hypothesis that it is possible to differentiate phenotypes on the basis of pressure signals applying transfer learning. From the data obtained, spectrogram images have been created using the Chronux library and Sonic Visualizer software. These images have fed three different pre-trained models: AlexNet, GoogLeNet and ResNet50.

The classification results for the validation set show that minimum accuracy obtained for all the experiments is 96% reaching 100% for the CNN AlexNet using the images generated with the spectrograms from Sonic Visualizer and some configurations with the Chronux library. This paper also presents the training and evaluation times showing that the computation times for the CNNs range from 35 minutes with AlexNet to 4 hours with ResNet50.

To sum up, it is concluded that it is possible to perform strain classification for animal model, using a recording system composed of a piezoelectric platform measuring pressure and a top camera. This system allows experiments to be carried out in a non-invasive way, offering high sensitivity measurements, making it possible to establish differences between distinct strains and classify them with high accuracy, precision, recall and F1 score values.

As future work, we could obtain spectrogram parameters automatically and integrate this step in the whole algorithm with a grid search to improve the efficiency. Moreover, we plan to apply this approach to an experimental study on healthy ageing in the elderly, where we are collecting data from a walking platform and an electroencephalogram (EEG) to identify gait anomalies.

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